

ACTIVITIES FOR DEVELOPING STRATEGIC COMPETENCE OF B2 LEVEL STUDENTS

Khodiyeva Yulduz Yunusovna

Master's student of Navoi state pedagogical institute

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Abstract. This article analyzes the essence, importance, methods and technology of developing strategic competence of a B2 level student.

Keywords: B2 level, strategic competence, method, language, knowledge.

МЕРОПРИЯТИЯ ПО РАЗВИТИЮ СТРАТЕГИЧЕСКОЙ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТИ СТУДЕНТОВ УРОВНЯ В2

Аннотация. В данной статье анализируются сущность, важность, методы и технологии развития статистической компетентности студента уровня В2.

Ключевые слова: уровень В2, стратегическая компетентность, метод, язык, знания.

INTRODUCTION

Most discussion will be given to describing the *communicative language competences* required to communicate effectively at B2 level. However, before this, readers should become familiar with some of the general competences illustrated below in figures 1-4. These are discussed in greater detail in the full text of the CEFR (2001: 101-108).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. General competences

Fig. 1 Declarative knowledge

Fig. 2 Skills and know-how

Fig. 3 Existential competence

Fig. 4 Ability to learn

RESULTS

Linguistic competences at B2 level

- Can express him/herself clearly and without much sign of having to restrict what he/she wants to say.

Has a sufficient range of language to be able to give clear descriptions, express viewpoints and develop arguments without much conspicuous searching for words.

- Has a good range of vocabulary for matters connected to his/her field and most general topics. Can vary formulation to avoid frequent repetition, but lexical gaps can still cause hesitation and circumlocution.

Lexical accuracy is generally high, though some confusion and incorrect word choice does occur without hindering communication, a clear, natural, pronunciation and intonation have acquired.

DISCUSSION

Sociolinguistic competences

- Can express him or herself confidently, clearly and politely in a formal or informal register, appropriate to the situation and person(s) concerned.

- Can with some effort keep up with and contribute to group discussions even when speech is fast and colloquial.

- Can sustain relationships with native speakers without unintentionally amusing or irritating them or requiring them to behave other than they would with a native speaker.

Discourse competences at B2 level

Flexibility

- Can adjust what he/she says and the means of expressing it to the situation and the recipient and adopt a level of formality appropriate to the circumstances.

- Can adjust to the changes of direction, style and emphasis normally found in conversation.

- Can vary formulation of what he/she wants to say.

Turntaking (also described under interaction strategies)

- Can intervene appropriately in discussion, exploiting appropriate language to do so.

- Can initiate, maintain and end discourse appropriately with effective turntaking.

CONCLUSIONS

Functional competences at B2 level

Spoken fluency

- Can communicate spontaneously, often showing remarkable fluency and ease of expression in even longer complex stretches of speech.

- Can produce stretches of language with a fairly even tempo; although he/she can be hesitant as he/she searches for patterns and expressions, there are few noticeably long pauses.

- Can interact with a degree of fluency and spontaneity that makes regular interaction with native speakers quite possible without imposing strain on either party.

Propositional precision

- Can pass on detailed information reliably.

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